

OSTEOPATHIC MANIPULATIVE TREATMENT IMPROVES OUTCOMES AFTER HEART SURGERY: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL

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SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Appendix 1

Rehabilitation program, psychological evaluation and Osteopathic manipulative treatment

All of the patients followed the same rehabilitation program and received usual care.

Within 24 hours of admission, they started a standardized physical therapy protocol

consisting of supervised physical training with five daily sessions of cycling at 70% maximal

heart rate for up to 50 minutes every week in accordance with the international guidelines

[1]. This was continued throughout the period of hospitalization for a mean of 20.4 ± 5.75

days, depending on the patients' clinical condition. They also underwent assisted respiratory

training for the prophylaxis of pulmonary complications [2]. The breathing exercises were

designed to help patients take long deep breaths with the aid of an inspiratory volume

incentivator device in order to counteract their decreased postoperative vital capacity. After

being instructed on how to use the device, the subjects were asked to inhale slowly, hold

their breath for at least five seconds, and then exhale normally.

The psychological characteristics of the patients related to the disease experience were

evaluated using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) [3], a self-assessment

scale for detecting symptoms of anxiety and depression in non-psychiatric in-patients. This

consists of two 7-item scales (one for anxiety and one for depression) with each item scored

from 0 to 3, and total score of 0-21 for each scale.

Patients in the treated group started osteopathic manipulative treatment (OMT) upon

admission to the cardiac rehabilitation unit the day after being discharged from the surgery

department. The standardized treatment was administered by an experienced osteopath

and physiotherapist. The conscious subjects were treated in supine position in order to

facilitate greater diaphragmatic excursion. The treatment consisted of a fixed and

preordained sequence of three sessions, beginning with the costal arch on the diaphragm, moving to the sternal area and, finally, to the region of the thoracic outlet. The first two phases were performed with the operator on the right side of the bed, the third phase with the operator on the head of the bed, as previously described [3-4]. As first step, the operator's hands were positioned on the anterior-lateral side of the chest, at the diaphragmatic level; the thumbs were put under the costal arch, while the other fingers were opened like a fan over the ribs (Figure A1, left-panel). The thoracic wall was then gently manipulated by the osteopath for some minutes. As second step, the operator moved his right hand over the sternal area, putting the left hand on the corresponding back side (Figure A1- central panel). Finally the operator moved to the head of the bed. In standing position, he put his hands on the upper area of the chest, in the supra-clavicular region, softly keeping the clavicles with the second and third fingers of both hands, while the thumbs were put at the seventh cervical or first dorsal spine level, and the fourth and fifth fingers were laid above the anterior chest wall (Figure A1- right panel).

This technique, even if applied on the painful areas, did not induce pain exacerbation because the thorax was palpated by applying a low pressure load directly on the skin, in the direction of resistance, without any sliding over the skin or forcing of the subcutaneous tissue, until it began to yield with a sensation of softening [5]. Sterile procedures were used when touching the patients on the surgical site. The entire osteopathic procedure took about fifteen minutes (approximately five minutes for each of the three regions), and was carried out once a day for five consecutive days. Only six patients required five minutes more time, spent on the diaphragm because of the significant strain associated with spreading the anterior thoracic wall and sternum.

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Figure A1. Illustration of the three phases of the Osteopathic Manipulative Treatment (OMT).

First the thoracic wall is gently manipulated by the operator's hands positioned on the anterior-lateral side of the chest, at the diaphragmatic level, with the thumbs under the costal arch and the other fingers over the ribs, for about 5 minutes (*left panel*). Then the operator continues the manipulation for other 5 minutes moving his right hand over the sternal area, and the left hand on the back side (*central panel*). Finally, the operator puts his hands on the supra-clavicular region, softly keeping the clavicles with the second and third fingers of both hands, while the thumbs are put at the seventh cervical or first dorsal spine level, and the fourth and fifth fingers are laid above the anterior chest wall (*right panel*). Also this third phase of manipulation lasts for 5 minutes.

Appendix 2

As additional statistical analysis for interval data we calculated the paired changes from T0 to T1 in each subject, and tested differences between groups in increments or decrements at the end of rehabilitation by the Mann-Whitney test. Data tested in this way were the VAS score, the inspiratory volume and the distance walked in the 6MWT. Results are reported in Table A2.

Table A2. Changes in interval data from admission (T0) to discharge (T1): mean (SD).

	CNT	OMT	p
VAS score	-1.50 (2.11)	-2.48 (2.35)	0.02
Inspiratory Volume (mL)	+575 (421)	+1037 (570)	<0.001
Walked Distance in 6 minutes (m)	+141 (75)	+147 (80)	0.89

p from Mann-Whitney test

Appendix 3

Table A3. Prevalence of comorbidities and cardiovascular risk factors, separately in treated (OMT) and control patients

Comorbidities	OMT N (%)	Controls N (%)	p
<i>Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm</i>	1 (2.5%)	0 (0.0%)	>0.99
<i>Adult celiac disease</i>	1 (2.5%)	0 (0.0%)	>0.99
<i>Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia</i>	5 (12.5%)	3 (7.5%)	0.71
<i>Benign Solid Tumor</i>	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.5%)	>0.99
<i>Chronic Hepatitis B or C</i>	2 (5.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0.49
<i>Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)</i>	3 (7.5%)	3 (7.5%)	>0.99
<i>Chronic peptic ulcer disease</i>	1 (2.5%)	0 (0.0%)	>0.99
<i>Chronic Renal Failure</i>	2 (5.0%)	2 (5.0%)	>0.99
<i>Colon Polyps</i>	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	>0.99
<i>Deficiency Anemia</i>	1 (2.5%)	0 (0.0%)	>0.99
<i>Gout</i>	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.5%)	>0.99
<i>History of cancer</i>	2 (5.0%)	3 (7.5%)	>0.99
<i>HIV infection</i>	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.5%)	>0.99
<i>Hypo or Hyperthyroidism</i>	2 (5.0%)	2 (5.0%)	>0.99
<i>Inherited metabolic disorders</i>	1 (2.5%)	0 (0.0%)	>0.99
<i>Lymphoma</i>	1 (2.5%)	2 (5.0%)	0.62
<i>Non vascular neurologic disorders</i>	1 (2.5%)	2 (5.0%)	0.62
<i>Obesity (stage 1 or 2)</i>	3 (7.5%)	2 (5.0%)	>0.99
<i>Obstructive Sleep Apnoea Syndrome (OSAS)</i>	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	>0.99
<i>Osteoporosis</i>	1 (2.5%)	3 (7.5%)	0.62
<i>Peripheral Vascular Disease</i>	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	>0.99
<i>Thrombocytopenia</i>	1 (2.5%)	0 (0.0%)	>0.99
Cardiovascular Risk Factors			
<i>Smoke</i>	17 (42.5%)	15 (37.5%)	0.82
<i>Hypertension</i>	26 (65%)	20 (50%)	0.13
<i>Dyslipidemia</i>	20 (50%)	20 (50%)	>0.99